

ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN ASPECTS OF INCREASING THE EXCLUSIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS THROUGH TEACHING THE HISTORY OF MEDICINE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154469>

Annotation. In this article, the main aspects of increasing the exclusive competence of students by teaching the history of medicine are analyzed through foreign literature.

Keywords: methodology, medical deontology, medical practice, social principle, humanities, empirical research, didactic opportunity.

Ensuring the effectiveness of education through the use of innovative, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is one of the most urgent issues today. In the process of teaching the history of medicine to students, it is important to teach them observation, creativity and independent mastering of advanced pedagogical practices. In this place, the teacher should pay special attention to the formation of the skills of education, the ability to allocate attention during the education process, the ability to control mental states and the culture of pedagogical techniques. In the process of teaching the history of medicine based on pedagogical technologies, the scope of the teacher's and student's activities is clearly defined, and the specific technology of the organization of education is shown.

Also, by using exclusive technologies to increase the competence of students, their ability to acquire knowledge and skills will be increased, and theoretical, clinical, analytical, creative and modern thinking of students will be perfected during training. Therefore, the application of innovative educational technologies to the process of studying the history of medicine is the most important condition today.

Effective use of the achievements of science, technology and advanced technology according to the purpose, tasks, content, methodical requirements of imparting knowledge to students is one of the urgent problems facing today's education system. Exclusive educational technologies help to increase students' passion and interest in knowledge, solid mastery of knowledge, develop skills and abilities to freely use them in practice, and lead to high efficiency.

In teaching the history of medicine, it is appropriate to choose exclusive educational technologies based on the didactic task of each lesson.

In the course of medical education, it is possible to use developing methods to train students as creative, creative thinkers in the teaching of the history of medicine. For example, solving non-standard problems related to the history of medicine, in which the student remembers and applies some new solution methods.

During the practical lessons of the science, the focus is on solving real or medical historical situations as close as possible to professional activity within the framework of roundtable discussions and exercises. For example, preparation for conference presentations will focus on solving a specific historical and scientific problem or task, which is the goal of source or historiographical research. This situation ensures the establishment of mutual relations between the teacher and students, observing the principles of partnership and cooperation. As a result, the student acquires the necessary knowledge base in science, which is the criterion for evaluating the performance of the activity. For example, the study of sources related to the history of medicine, the study and analysis of historiography, annotated articles, etc.

Students' initial familiarization with the educational topic, its categorical apparatus, personal participation of students in the process of searching and choosing the principles characteristic of the studied historical period, allows to successfully use active teaching methods in explaining the development of medicine.

Students should independently create a scheme based on the knowledge gained within the framework of their independent work and observe the logical connection between theoretical discoveries in natural sciences (physics, mathematics, chemistry, biology) and theoretical discoveries in the development of anatomy, physiology and other sciences. In addition, within this model, interaction in education can be built between a teacher and a student or a small group, as well as in an audience of students. This method promotes an active form of learning through students' acquisition of knowledge by making operative connections, drawing sequences, and sharing ideas. Students can do this type of independent work both in the classroom and outside of class (individually or in small groups).

The application of the operational-activity model implies the study of the history of medicine through distance learning with the use of individual (or small groups) tasks of students, including computer technologies and automated forms of supervision.

Students should learn to make interdisciplinary connections and understand the importance of the subjects included in the curriculum of a particular specialty (medicine, treatment-preventive work, dentistry, pediatrics, pharmacy, etc.). The development of students' ability to form fast connections helps to perform the following types of tasks:

- operationalization of the main categories;
- making comparative analytical tables;
- solving situational problems.

In addition, the principle of consistent formation of task questions within the subject allows to follow the evolution of ideas and helps to prepare students to solve problems, which creates a basis for the formation of professional competencies.

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